

Project acronym: CS3MESH4EOSC

Deliverable D4.3: Report on challenges and guidelines for collaborative user communities

Contractual delivery date	21-10-2022
Actual delivery date	30-06-2022
Grant Agreement no.	863353
Work Package	WP4
Nature of Deliverable	R (Report)
Dissemination Level	PU (Public)
Lead Partner	Fundacion ESADE
Document ID	CS3MESH4EOSC-22-019
Authors	Angelo Romasanta (ESADE), Gokhan Gulden (ESADE), Gozal Ahmadova (ESADE), Gideon van den Berg (ESADE)

Disclaimer:

The document reflects only the authors' views and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 863353

Versioning and Contributions History

Version	Date	Authors	Notes
0.1	30.06.2022	Angelo Romasanta (ESADE), Gokhan Gulten (ESADE), Gozal Ahmadova (ESADE)	
0.2	11.10.2022	Angelo Romasanta (ESADE), Gokhan Gulten (ESADE), Gozal Ahmadova (ESADE), Gideon van den Berg (ESADE)	

Index

Index of Figures	4
Index of Tables.....	5
Glossary.....	6
Executive Summary.....	7
1 Introduction	8
2 Cloud Computing, Open Science, and FAIR Data	9
2.1 Advantages provided by cloud computing and digital infrastructures	9
2.2 Challenges in cloud computing and digital infrastructures	10
2.3 The Promise of FAIR data and Open Science.....	12
3 Methods.....	14
3.1 Data Collection.....	14
3.2 Data Analysis.....	16
4 Results	17
4.1 Opportunities in the Science Mesh	17
4.2 Challenges in adoption	20
4.2.1 Awareness.....	21
4.2.2 Consideration.....	22
4.2.3 Use	23
4.2.4 Advocacy.....	24
5 Conclusions and Next Steps	25
6 Guidelines towards adoption of the Science Mesh.....	26
7 References	28
Annex.....	32

Index of Figures

Figure 1. The structure of stakeholders in universities and the cloud service uses (Sultan 2010).10

Figure 2. Federated mesh as a solution to the fragmented cloud problem (Romasanta and Wareham 2021).14

Figure 3. Illustration of the Science Mesh Services with respect to Applications, Federation Layer, and Cloud Storage Systems.15

Figure 4. Data structure (SM, Science Mesh).17

Figure 5. Capacities granted by digital infrastructures to researchers.18

Figure 6. Stylized adoption journey towards the Science Mesh.21

Figure 7. The result of the awareness of the Science Mesh in the scientific community, the perceived security and privacy issues, and the openness for adopting new cloud services.21

Index of Tables

Table 1. Comparison of cloud setups in enabling FAIR principles (adapted from go-fair.org).	13
Table 2. The interview list for the data collection with respect to the targeted groups.	16
Table 3. The role and impacts of FAIR digital infrastructures.	19
Table 4. The future expectations of the research community from cloud computing.	24
Table 5. Stakeholder engagement.	27

Glossary

Acronym	Name
APIs	Application Programming Interfaces
CC	Cloud computing
CS3	CS3 Community
CS3MESH4EOSC	The Science Mesh Project
DI	Digital infrastructure
EC	European Commission
ECI	European Cloud Initiative
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
NIST	The National Institute of Standards and Technology
PaaS	Platform as a Service
SaaS	Software as a Service
SLAs	Service Level Agreements
SMEs	Small Medium Enterprise
OCM	Open Cloud Mesh
OECD	Economic Co-operation and Development

Executive Summary

The Science Mesh is an initiative under the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), enabling the seamless transfer of data among researchers. Despite the enthusiasm for these FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data and Open Science-enabling infrastructures from policymakers and the scientific community, the research community still do not understand how they can be leveraged to advance their research goals. To address this gap, this report looks at the challenges in the adoption of such infrastructure and proposes guidelines on how these infrastructures can maximize engagement with researchers. By studying how to overcome the Science Mesh adoption barriers, this report aims to inform the scientific community and policymakers on how to accelerate the adoption of Open Science practices and maximize the future impact of infrastructures such as the Science Mesh.

Keywords: FAIR data, Digital infrastructure, Scientific community, Open Science

1 Introduction

The digital age has led to an extraordinary amount of opportunity to enhance the conduct of science. One of its leading technologies, namely cloud computing, has enabled researchers to access vast computing power and storage capacity. In turn, this has enabled researchers to pursue cutting-edge research by leveraging the tremendous amounts of data generated from, amongst other sources, various instruments and computational simulations. Aside from increasing computational capacity, cloud computing has enabled researchers to collaborate remotely. Researchers from diverse domains can now work together on challenging scientific problems. The sharing of data and knowledge among scientists and across research communities has long been acknowledged as critical in solving the increasingly complex challenges facing society (e.g., Walport and Brest, 2011; Vicente-Saez and Martinez-Fuentes, 2018).

The rise of cloud computing has, however, also brought its own set of challenges. Research organizations are concerned about data sovereignty, security, and privacy. They are also wary of the growing power of large technology companies that hold their data, making them susceptible to vendor lock-in. Concurrently, policymakers are increasingly demanding for data to be openly accessible for further reuse by other researchers.

To address these issues, policymakers have funded technology-development projects which will aid researchers in first, securing their data, and second, in sharing these data with collaborating researchers. One example of such a project is the Science Mesh (hereafter, the Mesh; sciencemesh.io); an initiative funded by the European Union which proposes to connect current research data services through vendor-neutral application programming interfaces (APIs) and protocols. When implemented, the Mesh will create a trusted, secure, and federated virtual environment, enabling research data to be shared across sovereignty borders and scientific disciplines.

Despite the enthusiasm from policymakers and research funders, many individual scientists still do not understand the promises of such infrastructures to advance their research objectives (Houtkoop et al. 2018; Rowhani-Farid, Allen, and Barnett 2017). To ensure that the Mesh would be adopted by researchers, studies focusing on the end-users must be conducted to validate the fulfilment of a significant scientific need. Currently, the Mesh is predicated on the idea that “if you build it, people will come.” Yet, adopting the Mesh as a solution for the issues detailed above is unlikely to be straightforward due to factors such as inertia from existing workflows, differences in incentive structures, and switching costs. As such, there is a need to further understand the challenges in the adoption of the Mesh and to explore what could make the Mesh more compelling for researchers. In this report, we investigate the various use-cases of the Mesh and researchers’ perceptions of the opportunities and challenges involved. The report aims to answer the following research questions:

- What opportunities does the Science Mesh open to users in the scientific community?
- What are the challenges to adoption from the scientific community?

Herewith, we conduct an inductive qualitative study of the Science Mesh, interviewing different stakeholders. Our study finds that the Science Mesh will perform various bridging roles that augment researchers’ workflows. We organize these capabilities in a framework; thereafter, we discuss the different challenges that occur along the adoption journey (i.e., awareness, followed by consideration, use, and advocacy).

The remainder of this report is structured as follows; in Section 2, we review the scientific cloud computing literature, focusing on its current opportunities and challenges; in addition, we place the Science Mesh in the context of FAIR Data and Open Science. In Section 3 and 4, we present the

research methodology (i.e., data collection strategy and analysis) and results, respectively, with a focus on addressing the specific research questions mentioned previously. Finally, in Section 5 and 6, we provide recommendations for the successful adoption of the Science Mesh.

Importantly, this report does not only provide recommendations related to this specific infrastructure but to all other digital infrastructures (DIs) working towards Open Science and FAIR data.

2 Cloud Computing, Open Science, and FAIR Data

We begin this section by reviewing how researchers currently engage with data on the cloud and what advantages they benefit from. Thereafter, we discuss the challenges preventing researchers from using it to its full potential, with a focus on the challenges of fragmentation and lack of interoperability. Finally, we explore how these challenges can be overcome to fulfil the promises of Open Science and FAIR practices.

2.1 Advantages provided by cloud computing and digital infrastructures

The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) describes the following advantages offered by cloud computing: ubiquitous, convenient, rapidly provisioned, with minimal management effort, and service provider interaction (Caldarelli, Ferri, and Maffei 2017). Apart from these elements, the cloud has also had great societal impact due to increased global collaboration, reduced opportunity costs, resource rationalization, scalability, access to the global base of users, increased opportunities that can be explored, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, agility of process and computational agility, and increased mobility and portability (Caldarelli, Ferri, and Maffei 2017; Branco, De Sá-Soares, and Rivero 2017; Yang et al. 2014; Ferri, Spanò, and Tomo 2020; Kurze et al. 2011; Ross and Blumenstein 2015).

Compared to traditional computing systems, cloud computing has provided superior economic benefits by removing most of the upfront costs (Toosi, Calheiros, and Buyya 2014). Cloud computing systems offer cost savings for customers as they do not need to build IT infrastructure or purchase hardware. Additionally, the cost of electricity consumption and cooling down hardware is also reduced in this circumstance (Sultan 2010). As it requires fewer people to maintain the infrastructure, the labour costs of organizations are also less (Sultan 2010). In addition to the customers, the vendors also benefit from cloud computing as they operate in massive data warehouses to offer cloud services to customers at high density. The economies of scale provide relatively cheap prices to customers as the IT management costs per use also decrease (Ross and Blumenstein 2015; Kurze et al. 2011).

According to NIST, there are three service models of cloud computing, namely SaaS (Software as a Service), PaaS (Platform as a Service) and IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service) (Zhang, Wu, and Cheung 2013). IaaS refers to remotely offering a full computer infrastructure to its users (e.g., virtual computers and storage devices). IaaS has the responsibility to ensure that the applications and software are running smoothly. Some commercial IaaS providers include IBM, Google, and Amazon EC2 (Almajalid 2017; Sultan 2010; Zhang, Wu, and Cheung 2013). PaaS is situated between the software and infrastructure that ensures optimal performance of the applications that end-users may design, test, and deploy (Sultan 2010; Almajalid 2017; Ross and Blumenstein 2015). Some providers of PaaS include the Google App Engine and Globus Genomics (Charlebois, Palmour, and Knoppers 2016; Zhang, Wu, and Cheung 2013). Finally, SaaS includes applications which are offered to clients via the internet that can only be used on the cloud infrastructure (i.e., without installing or keeping the

software on the hardware or computer) (Sultan 2010). Some SaaS providers include Dropbox, NetSuite, Google, Citrix, and Salesforce.com (Almajalid 2017; Charlebois, Palmour, and Knoppers 2016).

In the academic setting, Sultan (2010) explores how different stakeholders interact with these three cloud-computing service models (Figure 1). Typically, students and staff engage with software such as email accounts, communications, and productivity applications. On the other hand, researchers typically require special software and hardware to run experiments which involve more processing and computation power. Finally, even within academic institutions, developers are required for the writing and hosting of applications for various users.

Figure 1. The structure of stakeholders in universities and the cloud service uses (Sultan 2010).

Focusing further on the research community, cloud computing has enabled researchers to leverage the advances in computing power and storage capacity together with the decreasing hardware cost (Foster et al. 2008). Furthermore, it has enabled users to deal with the exponential growth in data generated from instrumentation, simulations, and archiving. Aside from addressing the computational needs of individual researchers, the cloud also has impacted the way research is conducted worldwide (Jankowski, 2007; Chen and Zhang, 2014; Yang *et al.*, 2014). More specifically, it has enabled researchers to assemble different datasets from various sources and access vast computational resources using only their laptops.

2.2 Challenges in cloud computing and digital infrastructures

Despite its overall benefits, challenges still exist that limit scientists from using DIs to their full potential. The challenges of cloud computing include: data security, data privacy, vendor lock-in problems, reliability, performance issues, lack of flexibility and agility, data ownership problems, standardization issues, complexity, lack of flexibility and scalability, lack of service level agreements (SLAs), and lack of interoperability (Oliveira, Thomas, and Espadanal 2014; Yang et al. 2012; Sadashiv and Kumar 2011; Foster et al. 2008; Almajalid 2017; Kurze et al. 2011). Proposing a framework to categorize these, Caldarelli et al. (2017) categorized the challenges in cloud computing into four segments, namely organizational issues, technical issues, legal issues, and general risks (e.g., In data protection and privacy) (Caldarelli, Ferri, and Maffei 2017).

Using this categorization, organizational issues can arise from management changes within the cloud service provider (e.g., acquisitions or restructuring) that can ultimately lead to service failure. Therefore, the long-term viability of the cloud service provider is highly important to facilitate trust within their customers (Foster et al. 2008). Additionally, Caldarelli et al. (2017) discussed that any loss

of service provider reputation may affect the customers' preferences, given that customers may collaborate with other users or provide a third-party service through the cloud system; thus, reputation loss indeed may damage the general business of the provider, as well as the preferences and trust in customers (Caldarelli, Ferri, and Maffei 2017). Performance instability is also considered an organizational issue that may hinder the adoption of cloud computing (Sharma et al. 2016; Sadashiv and Kumar 2011).

Technical issues encapsulate the technical readiness of the cloud service; as such, various issues stem for this category, namely resource-sharing isolation problems, shared technology vulnerabilities, cloud cross-compatibility, data leakage, and system integrity (Caldarelli, Ferri, and Maffei 2017; Toosi, Calheiros, and Buyya 2014; Pankaj et al. 2009). Within these technical issues, security issues are also considered an additional major barrier to the adoption of cloud computing, given that customers or clients may be concerned about their data confidentiality and integrity; moreover, customer concerns related to the nature of their data storage (i.e., how and where) are expected, given that customers do not have information regarding physical storage places (El-Gazzar, Hustad, and Olsen 2016; Foster et al. 2008). Thus, security and privacy concerns ultimately have a negative effect on the adoption of cloud computing in organizations (Oliveira, Thomas, and Espadanal 2014). In addition, it is argued that customers may have undetailed SLAs which leads to data storage and security opacity (El-Gazzar, Hustad, and Olsen 2016).

Legal issues refer to the risks resulting from changes of jurisdiction and the liabilities the cloud service providers would face in the case of service interruption and the loss of data. Currently, there is a lack of standardization in cloud computing with respect to legal jurisdiction and data legislation in countries, this in turn creates a substantial barrier to cloud computing adoption, as users generally do not know what would happen in the case of various incidents (Caldarelli, Ferri, and Maffei 2017; Charlebois, Palmour, and Knoppers 2016; El-Gazzar, Hustad, and Olsen 2016). On the other hand, strong regulations are always considered to hamper the innovation process in general. It is also argued that high regulatory measures within cloud computing to ensure data security and privacy will most likely hinder the innovation and adoption of cloud computing in organizations (El-Gazzar, Hustad, and Olsen 2016).

The previously mentioned risks and challenges focus on individual cloud service providers. However, there is another large issue that is related to the overall cloud landscape; that is, how different cloud providers relate and interact with one another. Given the current lack of standardization and interoperability in cloud services, the adoption of heterogeneous cloud services creates fragmentation. These fragmented clouds do not allow users to collaborate and exchange information freely, which creates an additional barrier to the adoption of cloud computing (Romasanta and Wareham 2021). Interoperability refers to the ability of cloud providers to work in harmony, ultimately implying that different cloud systems can function and interact together (Zhang, Wu, and Cheung 2013). Toosi et al. (2014) discussed the motivation for interoperability and having an interoperable cloud service; ultimately, they found that interoperability provides end-users with improved scalability and wider resource availability in the cloud service domain. Additionally, interoperability leads to cost efficiency and reduced energy consumption, two very important items of concern with respect to the financial stability and environmental sustainability of organizations (Toosi, Calheiros, and Buyya 2014). It is crucial to have an environment of cloud providers or vendors which supports more than one operating system, database and APIs through standard interfaces or brokering that enables a service broker to translate messages between the different cloud services and interfaces (Gupta, Seetharaman, and Raj 2013; Yang et al. 2012; 2014; Toosi, Calheiros, and Buyya 2014).

Despite this, achieving interoperability across cloud services is not straightforward. First, the technical readiness of a specific cloud service may not be compatible with another, and as such,

achieving interoperability may be difficult due to cross-administration domains and data service issues (Foster et al. 2008). Additionally, the interoperability perspective may vary substantially among users and the providers given that their respective goals over the long-term may not necessarily complement one another. This dissociation is likely given that end-users may want full control on the cloud, where they can migrate the services and collaborate with others freely; providers, on the other hand, may not desire a fully interoperable service, thus ensuring customers are retained within their service, more customers are attracted from outside, and their market share is increased (Zhang, Wu, and Cheung 2013).

Ultimately, the lack of interoperability creates downstream challenges for users, with switching costs from one provider to another leading to vendor lock-in. Toosi et al. (2014) further describes how this problem arises when customers require services tailored to their specific needs, which in turn, makes the future relocation of resources highly costly, and difficult to obtain and integrate into the system (Toosi, Calheiros, and Buyya 2014). Moreover, organizations may have financial limitations and even outstanding contracts with providers that lead them to difficulties when searching for alternative cloud services (Ross and Blumenstein 2015).

2.3 The Promise of FAIR data and Open Science

Overcoming these fragmentation challenges would open new opportunities in science. With the exponential increase in the amount of data generated by the scientific community in the past decade, there is a demand for good data management and stewardship practices (Madduri et al. 2019). To help scientists deal with and leverage these data, there has been a call to embrace FAIR data principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Mons et al. 2017). In the context of FAIR data, the term findable refers to data that is clearly labelled with the appropriate metadata and indexed in a searchable registry, allowing efficient searchability for both humans and machines. The term accessible refers to data that can be accessed through standardized communications protocols after granting proper authorizations. The term interoperable refers to data that can be easily used across different environments and potentially integrated with other datasets. Finally, the term reusable refers to data that is well-described, allowing it to be replicated and even extended for other uses (Tenopir et al. 2015).

Principle	Description	Current setting	How the Science Mesh can solve this
Findable	Metadata and data are easy to find for both humans and computers.	Data may not be properly labelled for easy search.	Data can be easily labelled thanks to specialized applications offered as part of the Science Mesh environment.
Accessible	Once data is found, they can be accessed with authorisation and authentication.	Data may be stored in silos that are difficult to access.	Data can be accessed through existing robust authentication systems.
Interoperable	Data can be readily used by applications for	Data and apps to open them may only	Data and apps can be used across systems

	analysis, storage, and processing.	work in their original platform.	through an interoperability layer.
Reusable	Metadata and data are well-described for replication and integration.	Data is stored or archived without thinking about reusability.	Tools are deployed to integrate reusability in the workflow.

Table 1. Comparison of cloud setups in enabling FAIR principles (adapted from go-fair.org).

FAIR principles have been embraced by many advocates within the scientific community and policymaking circles. On the one hand, achieving FAIR data reduces the various inefficiencies found in the scientific process, including wasted time, additional storage costs, extra license costs, and double funding (European Commission 2019). Within the EU, the most recent overall cost of lacking FAIR data has been estimated at EUR 10.2 billion per year (European Commission 2019). Moreover, the cloud has been lauded for its potential to reduce waste from unused research data (Tenopir et al. 2015; Madduri et al. 2019). Typically, when researchers finish their projects, they store their data in silos, never to be used again. However, other researchers may find new uses for this data that were previously unthought-of when they were first collected by the original researchers.

Beyond reducing inefficiencies, FAIR data promises to open new frontiers in human knowledge. For one, by making data FAIR, researchers can reuse data and find other applications for it previously unforeseen by the original researchers who first collected it. Moreover, FAIR enables international collaborations, bringing together teams with different specializations to collaborate on specific scientific problems (Wise et al. 2019). Through these collaborations, scientists can pursue previously unimagined lines of scientific inquiry – an area of science referred to as e-science. As an example of this transformation in science, Burgelman et al. (2019) documents how the Ebola and Zika epidemics were addressed quickly with researchers sharing datasets for the public to access. This openness facilitated the rapid development of an experimental vaccine. Beyond this, with FAIR data, the scientific community can unlock the full potential of advances in computational technologies; more specifically, machines can sort through existing data, assemble relevant datasets, and develop new insights (Jacobsen et al. 2020).

Pursuing FAIR data is an important step toward enabling Open Science. The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) defines Open Science as the access to scientific activities, data from public research, and collaborative research which is enabled by Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) (OECD, 2021). In the EU, EOSC aims to create a sole market to ensure data sovereignty and competitiveness of Europe in the global area, as well as to promote Open Science; an important aspect as scientists can share and access documents and data, as well as reuse those data to rerun experiments and analyse the previous problems. There are seven steps involved in the lifecycle of Open Science, namely preparation, discovery, analysis, writing, publication, outreach, and assessment (EOSC 2020).

Despite its ambitious promises, many researchers are still not aware of the FAIR movement. The State of Open Data report published by Digital Science (2018) found that just 15% of researchers were “familiar with FAIR principles”. In cases they are aware of it, the report by the EOSC Executive Board shows that they may be apathetic to it, given its unclear individual benefits and the perceived inconveniences of making data FAIR (European Commission 2020). The same report also found that some researchers do not think their data can be reused for other research at all. While the promises of FAIR data are admirable, barriers clearly exist at different levels (Geneviève et al. 2019; Van Panhuis et al. 2014; Lilleoere and Hansen 2011). For example, based on notions of data privacy and security, researchers may limit those who can access their data; political and socio-cultural barriers can make

researchers not willing to share their data; and financial constraints can also hinder researchers from investing in FAIR principles.

The Science Mesh aims to overcome these challenges through its federated mesh approach (Figure 2). However, given that studies on FAIR DIs, such as the Science Mesh, are still lacking, this report aims to fill this gap and understand the opportunities and challenges in their adoption.

Figure 2. Federated mesh as a solution to the fragmented cloud problem (Romasanta and Wareham 2021).

3 Methods

3.1 Data Collection

This report is based on interviews with key stakeholders to identify the use-cases, advantages, and challenges in adopting innovative technologies in cloud storage. The first group of interviewees comprises the project owners that are already familiar with the project, given that they have prepared the project definition and received funding from the European Commission.

The second group of interviewees comprises the early adopters of the Science Mesh as a product; this group has awareness about the project and defined expectations. More specifically, we interviewed potential users of the four proposed application areas of the Science Mesh:

- *Data Science Environment* integrates Science Mesh with open-data repositories, which allows users to access the data processing environment remotely and to work on the analysis algorithms without any special setup. JupyterLab, QuantaStack, and Voilà are used in this service and the use cases of this service are the Earth Observation, run by the Joint Research Centre, EC JRC, and High Energy Physics, run by the Large Hadron Collider, LHC, at CERN.
- *Open Data Systems* allows the users to add metadata and to publish or share their datasets on the Science Mesh or external data repositories. Describo, InvenioRDM, and ScieboRDS are used in this service where the target users are researchers, data librarians, and policy makers.

- *Collaborative Documents* allows users to edit, comment, and revise their documents simultaneously, in real-time. Collabora integration is successfully integrated and OnlyOffice is planned to be used in this service.
- *On-Demand Data Transfer* allows users to transfer large datasets at high-speed between different servers in multiple countries. Rclone, FTS, and Rucio are used in this service.

These four services are summarized and illustrated in the context of applications, the federation layer, and the cloud storage systems (*Figure 3*). Figure 3 also consists of the product names for each service, which are already on the market and used separately, making the realization of the Science Mesh Project highly feasible.

Figure 3. Illustration of the Science Mesh Services with respect to Applications, Federation Layer, and Cloud Storage Systems.

Beyond adjacent stakeholders, the third group of interviewees comprises researchers not involved in the Science Mesh Project. The motive to include the third group is to understand how they use cloud computing in their research and their needs and/or expectations from cloud services. Their inclusion was necessary for the overall results to inform whether the Science Mesh product can be applied in their organization and whether the product meets their needs and expectations.

In summary, we conducted interviews with (i) project partners or stakeholders, (ii) early adopters of the Science Mesh, and (iii) research professionals who are not involved in the project. The primary motive to target these three different groups was to analyse the advantages and issues in cloud storage systems, to generate hypotheses about how the Science Mesh can be improved, and to address the current challenges.

The interview questions (presented in Annex I) were comprised of four main sections:

1. The Cloud Storage Overview: to understand the current cloud storage setup in the research community, the freedom that their current cloud storage provides, and the expectations to choose the cloud storage systems.
2. The Issues and Challenges: to reveal the priority of cloud storage systems in research organizations and the general challenges (e.g., privacy, security, legal, costs, type of

technology, and performance).

3. Use Cases: to answer how cloud storage is typically used in research and how much is it used to collaborate internally or externally, and their future expectations on cloud storage systems.
4. Adoption of innovative solutions in the organizations: to provide valuable information on the probable adoption challenges and overall concern about adopting new cloud systems.

Apart from the interviews (see Table 2 for detail), data was also collected from bi-weekly CS3MESH meetings, internal documents, monthly catch-up meetings with project partners, symposiums, workshops, conferences, and podcasts.

Organizations	Field	Application	Number of interviewees
Group 1 – Science Mesh Project Partners			
CERN	High energy physics	Remote Data Analysis	2
LOFAR	Astrophysics	Large data transfers	2
AARNET	Humanities	Data FAIRness	2
University of Münster	Medical Imaging	Collaborative Document editing	2
Group 2 – Science Mesh Early Adopters			
JRC	Earth Observation	Remote data analysis	2
CERN	High energy physics	Remote Data Analysis	1
University of Duisburg-Essen	Information Management	Sciebo	1
Group 3 – Scientific Community (General)			
SusPhos	Organic Chemistry	NA	1
FMP Berlin	Chemistry	NA	1
TU Bergakademie Freiberg	Geology and Environmental Sciences	NA	3
ETH Zurich	High energy physics	NA	1
University of Humboldt	Geography	NA	1
University of Bonn	Numerical Simulation	NA	1
UCLouvain	Organic Chemistry	NA	1

Table 2. The interview list for the data collection with respect to the targeted groups.

3.2 Data Analysis

In total, 17 interviews were conducted, recorded, and later transcribed to text. The qualitative data analysis was conducted by pinpointing keywords and quotes in each section of the interview for each participant. After determining the keywords and grouping the similar ones, the transcripts were analysed using the Gioia Methodology, coding for the first-order and emerging second-order themes.

The Gioia Methodology is critical as it provides a data structure for the research questions. Indeed, without a coherent data structure, theoretical insights and qualitative data analysis derived from interviews would be highly abstract (Gioia, Corley, and Hamilton 2013). It aims to find similarities among different categories, aiming to decrease the total number of categories and allowing more efficient data analysis. The aim of the 1st order codes is to generate categories stemming from the interviews, allowing a clearer perspective to become evident, while not deeply refining the categories. Within the 2nd order, however, different concepts related to the 1st order results are generated, with

the aim being to describe and clarify the phenomenon and/or research questions to obtain the for each grouping themes. The following figure offers a graphic representation of the entire process, including the raw data (i.e., the 1st order data) and the themes (i.e., the 2nd order data).

Figure 4. Data structure (SM, Science Mesh).

4 Results

We organize the following section by first exploring the current capabilities that researchers already use in their research workflows through existing digital tools. We also explore their limitations, giving us insight into the potential impact of FAIR practices once they are applied by researchers. Thereafter, we discuss the new capabilities in storage and analysis that FAIR DIs grant, by exploring the different early use-cases of the Science Mesh. Finally, we discuss the bridging role of DIs to transform potential impact to realized FAIR impacts.

4.1 Opportunities in the Science Mesh

Figure 5. Capacities granted by digital infrastructures to researchers.

Current digital tools already enable researchers to store their data according to most of their needs. On a basic level, researchers can upload their data into commercial “sync and share” services as a backup and for convenient access across any device. To cater to their specialized needs in privacy and security, research institutions are also setting up their own cloud services enabled by offerings such as OwnCloud, NextCloud, or SeaFile. Despite the benefits of these services, researchers are currently limited in their ability to share data with peers using other services, due to the lack of interoperability across providers. If these providers are not interoperable, researchers would either have to create a new account to match their collaborators or move data in and out of their cloud providers, which gives rise to additional barriers to sharing.

Apart from storage, many researchers leverage commercial cloud services to analyse their data. It is common for research teams to rent compute time from services like AWS or Azure to run their tasks at scale and only pay on a per-use basis. These services enable them to conduct such analyses effortlessly, abstracting the various complexities of the computing platform. Despite these conveniences, collaboratively conducting analysis tasks is not yet common. Moreover, there is a challenge in acquiring and assembling the data for analysis in the first place. Typically, once data is filed and archived, the potential for data to be revisited by other studies tends to be limited.

Theme		Illustrative quote	Barriers / Challenges	Priority for Science Mesh
Processes and resources familiar to researchers	Individual data storage	“I use it for backing up, storing my data and everyday data, review notes that are saved in that cloud, also all the data from my research projects is in there, some way or another”	Mature, convenient service offered by existing tech giants. Authority of the institution to choose cloud provider.	Low due to existence of good alternatives
	Individual data analysis	“Without having to download to your machine, or sending anywhere else, you can run the analysis directly”	Prevalence of established platforms; different computational needs	Low due to alternatives
Bridging role of FAIR digital	Storage to insights	“The Mesh is a federation of existing services, so, what	Individuals typically just store	High due to potential

infrastructures		we will be able to achieve hopefully is to bring together all the users from different services to create a much broader impact area for doing the research through aggregating the existing services and the existing data on the services"	files and never revisit them again. The need for infrastructures to promote serendipitous revisiting of stored data.	impact and lack of solutions
	Individuals to collective	"Promise to users to login once, and whatever search you do, all of the collaborators that you know about, or you want to work with are available through the interface whether they are on local storage or mesh sites"	Need for services individuals are already accustomed to, to be applicable in a collaborative setting.	High due to current barriers and impact
New capabilities granted to researchers leveraging Science Mesh	Data transfer to collaborators	"These cloud services are used for sharing some common information and tools as well... some [files] are quite big"	Existing mechanisms of data sharing such as email, link with data repositories, etc. Apathy on security and privacy concerns.	Medium due to inadequate solutions
	Collaborative data analysis	"It offers many possibilities in terms of just programming in a collaborative way instead of doing things on own side"	Requires a common language, a common set of standards for different platforms to communicate with each other.	High due to high demand use cases
	Data sharing to the community	"One use case of mesh is for researchers who want to share their data with [the] wider audience"	Technology not overcoming field-specific sociocultural norms; Low incentives for researchers	High due to lacking solutions
	Data reuse for community	"FAIR wants to fight against the data just sitting on your disk"	Enabling discovery across scientific disciplines	High due to lack of solutions

Table 3. The role and impacts of FAIR digital infrastructures.

The previous discussion explores the current functionalities in storage and analysis that researchers are accustomed to in their workflows. The Science Mesh promises to augment these functionalities in different ways. First, the Mesh can enable researchers to give other researchers access to their data easily. It can facilitate the process of authenticating which collaborators have rights to certain data,

and later, enable the transfer of data across different cloud services. More advanced functionalities enable researchers to sync and share files and folders in real-time across different providers. Through the Science Mesh, this functionality will be utilized, for instance, in astrophysics, where it is common for large amounts of data to be moved from site to site, where they are initially generated (e.g., telescopes) to the site where they have to be analysed (e.g., computing clusters). This process is typically cumbersome due to the large amounts of data needed to be transferred. The Mesh can play an important role in facilitating such transfers through user-friendly interfaces.

Instead of just enabling collaborations across known researchers, the Mesh can also facilitate data sharing with strangers. Through the Mesh, researchers from different fields can download data stored in repositories and find other uses for it. However, before this can be done, datasets have to be labelled with the proper metadata. The Science Mesh enables researchers to prepare, package, and publish their data from the comfort of the interface of their organizational sync and share provider. At the same time, researchers who would like to download the data can seamlessly move it to their own organizational node. Through such functionality, the Mesh then enables researchers to assemble powerful datasets from different sources for novel scientific insights.

Apart from bridging across storage providers, the Science Mesh can enable the collaborative analysis of data across research teams. Through the Mesh, researchers can analyse datasets located at a remote site without requiring data transfer. Researchers from different institutions can collaborate in writing code and see the output of such code responsively through browser-based interactive notebooks like Jupyter. This use is already being piloted in the highly collaborative field of earth observation. Typically, the research team that generates satellite images must collaborate with local partners, who then edit and process these images for their specific applications. Since transferring large amounts of data may not be the most appropriate for resource-constrained partners, the Science Mesh enables collaborative data analysis through a standard “Jupyter-like” notebook interface.

Finally, the analysis of data can be democratized to be open to the entire scientific community, instead of being limited to the original set of collaborators. For instance, digital archives in the humanities and social sciences are common, housing the records of different cultures and languages around the world. Through DIs like the Mesh, this rich data source can be made available to the entire scientific community such that they can be revisited in new research questions or reanalysed using new algorithms.

To realize the potential impact of FAIR, the Science Mesh can perform two important bridging functions; firstly, it can facilitate the transition from storage to analysis. Researchers already store data, but the problem is following up with this data to be used for other applications not foreseen initially. DIs bridge this by putting together all the tools in storage and analysis in one interface. Through this, researchers can readily use the data in storage for new applications. Secondly, transitioning from individual use to collaborative use is not straightforward. Thus, it can also play the important role of bridging between the individual to larger spheres of collaborations (i.e., from project partners to the larger scientific community). To illustrate this, instead of the inconvenience for each researcher to send their data to others, the Mesh can facilitate this activity. Users would not have to send an email to each potential data user, instead, this would be handled from a single interface.

4.2 Challenges in adoption

To organize the challenges in adopting the Science Mesh, we divide the following section into the main processes which researchers follow in their adoption of DIs, namely awareness of the service, consideration of whether to engage with the service, using the service in their workflow, and advocacy

to promote the service to their peers.

Figure 6. Stylized adoption journey towards the Science Mesh.

4.2.1 Awareness

The biggest challenge facing the Science Mesh is the lack of awareness about this DI as well as the broader movement towards Open Science and FAIR data. This is clearly indicated by *Figure 7*, which highlights interviewee awareness of the Science Mesh. Only one interviewee from the research community was aware of the Science Mesh Project, and this likely only due to the researcher’s specific background. As such, should the background of the scientist not overlap with the background of the Mesh Project partners (in this case, the background was data analysis in earth sciences), then the likelihood of recognition of the Science Mesh Project is very low. What is more surprising is that many scientists are not even aware of their own institutional cloud services, that they can take advantage of for their workflows.

Figure 7. The result of the awareness of the Science Mesh in the scientific community, the perceived security and privacy issues, and the openness for adopting new cloud services.

Moreover, the scientific community does not appear aware of the security issues of the cloud storage services they use. Despite this lack of knowledge, users in the scientific community continue to use the same services as they are cheaper or easier to use, or simply because users want to avoid making additional financial and time investments into implementing a new system.

Moreover, many researchers are either unaware or even apathetic to the pursuit of Open Science and FAIR data. As EOSC aims for Open Science and tries to create interoperable services so that

researchers can freely exchange information and contribute to science, many researchers still do not know the meaning of “Open Science”. There is also ambiguity in the meaning of “Open Science” and what is implied by the term. While the project partners may have a clear understanding of it, the research community doesn’t seem to, which may be a real challenge to motivate researchers to adopt the Science Mesh and be part of the wider Open Science ecosystem. The Science Mesh project team should highlight the meaning of the latter, why it is very important, how it will serve the progress of science and how the researchers are better off by contributing towards it.

4.2.2 Consideration

Once a researcher is aware of Open Science, FAIR data, and the Science Mesh, they will then assess whether they want to undertake the effort to learn how to use that particular DI. We find this step also highly critical to the success of the adoption of the Mesh, with many researchers wary of the learning curve needed to take advantage of it over existing solutions. Taking insights from the technology adoption literature, the criteria to consider here are namely, relative advantage, trialability, observability, complexity, and compatibility.

It is important that the service provides a greater advantage relative to current solutions. From our interviews with researchers who are currently not a part of the Science Mesh project, they use cloud services primarily for data storage. As a consequence, their main priority is storage size. As discussed above, the research groups and institutes may benefit from a cloud system for free as a part of an agreement between a public cloud provider and a university/laboratory, or for very low prices for limited functionality. However, those solutions end up being insufficient beyond certain limits, often due to the cost difference between basic and “premium” plans. The Science Mesh could act as a cost-effective solution which would foster sharing of resources across academia and research while providing a costing model which scales linearly rather than based on a threshold.

It is also crucial that users can observe and try the service. While this is foreseen to be possible later into the Project and there are already working prototypes of many of the components, the lack of a tangible and usable product which can be employed daily, in a real-world scenario, has hindered some of the efforts in the promotion of the Mesh to its potential users. We expect that to be solved further down the line.

Talking about complexity, the adoption of the Science Mesh in research facilities might be complex from other perspectives as well. Using commercial public services can be easier for researchers since they are already accustomed to their interfaces. Adopting a new interface may lead to costs in learning time and other resources. Additionally, the onboarding process is, for the moment, highly bureaucratic and cumbersome.

The last challenge to adoption is compatibility. This, however, is the easiest barrier to overcome for the Mesh. As it just operates on top of existing services which some users are already accustomed to, this is not difficult to overcome. One of the most important technical gains of the Science Mesh is that it is an “add-on service”, which means that the research centres, universities, and commercial partners which already possess an open-source sync and share solution will experience low friction in adoption. They will not spend additional resources to create new infrastructure; rather, they will only spend what is needed to accomplish the onboarding formalities and the well-documented technical steps which have to be performed to install an additional component which will sit on their existing solution. When the number of partners or users increases in the federated mesh, the cost of use per partner or user will decrease, which makes the Science Mesh cost-efficient when compared with a “single user” scenario.

4.2.3 Use

The perceived ease of using cloud services as well as the actual perceived usefulness of a specific cloud service are critical factors for researchers when adopting a cloud service. Moreover, researchers' time and financial resources are typically pivotal elements in their decision-making process when adopting workplans (including cloud services). Within this perspective, the Science Mesh may reduce time and financial pressure on researchers as it will (a) offer four online services that increases the speed of data analyses, and (b) decrease the cost of acquiring new software/hardware to run analyses and store data.

With the majority of researchers using cloud services for storage alone, there is a need to push them towards the more advanced collaborative functionalities offered by the Mesh. From our interviews, however (as reported above), the scientific community does not appear too excited about collaboration possibilities or sharing their data towards Open Science. This, however, is not an issue solely for the Science Mesh but also for the broader movement pushed by policymakers and research funders.

Studying how interviewees already use existing cloud services, some interviewees have pointed out that they have issues with simultaneous collaboration on the document, where some indicated that they lose the saved draft and therefore they have to work on the same process over again. The Science Mesh aims to integrate popular applications on the infrastructure, including applications such as CodiMD, Collabora, and OnlyOffice, enabling collaborative editing. Therefore, the Science Mesh would be a great choice for researchers who like to collaborate and simultaneously edit files.

It is important for the Science Mesh to emphasize how it would make the researcher's workflow easier, as they will be able to use this platform to perform many of their research tasks. As discussed previously, the Science Mesh will initially offer services in four areas, namely Data Science Environments, Open Data Systems, Collaborative Documents and On-Demand Data Transfers. Those services will enable researchers to save time, collaborate easily, to have more collaborations in different countries, to run data analysis software on their system directly, to transform large-scale data volumes across borders, and to share their research easily with the world. The services mentioned will have a secondary effect, which is rationalization of resources through sharing, for both storage and data analysis.

The Science Mesh offers great opportunities to form new alliances, to increase the speed of data analysis, to enable science to be open and without boundaries while ensuring data circulates according to data privacy regulations such as the GDPR. These opportunities may be the source of innovation in research. By increasing the data share speed and data analysis, researchers will obtain results much earlier and experience a decreased amount of bureaucracy, which sometimes can be a tough problem, especially across countries. This "accelerated data sharing" would open new doors to scientists using the platform.

Quotes: Future Expectations of Non-Mesh Users from Cloud Services	
Participant # 9	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• I would like to be able to have a visual map• metadata from the data you have is missing
Participant # 10	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• easier accessibility• privacy should be kept as high as possible• encryption is imperative.
Participant # 11	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• it would be cheaper for companies to use it

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I am worried about the environmental impacts of such internet activities • a really fast system that supports high volume of data sharing
Participant # 12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I would like to keep my data but currently it is not possible • it would be nice to have more auxiliary services to deal with the data in my own cloud • collaborative with other universities in Europe
Participant # 13	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • for everybody to use the same system
Participant # 14	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • for a special cloud that it is possible for encryption of information • more space for my files • live editing system • possibility to keep all versions of files
Participant # 15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • synchronize online what it is available offline wherever you are • Voice command would be nice, especially for big datasets • cloud storage device that combines/encrypts file
Participant # 16	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fast synchronization and uploading process • If I want to send this file, I want it to be encrypted, until it arrives to the end user
Participant # 17	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • special settings to received notifications

Table 4. The future expectations of the research community from cloud computing.

4.2.4 Advocacy

Finally, once users are already part of the Mesh, they can serve as ambassadors to further promote it. From our research, this seems to be the easiest part, as word of mouth spreads easily. As more universities and institutions become a part of the Science Mesh, more researchers will use the federated mesh and its services. In time, the high-quality products in Science Mesh will be recognized and become more popular among scientists and researchers. As the scientific community is in constant communication, more and more researchers will want to use the services, because of their regarded advantages. We believe the Science Mesh has the opportunity to gradually reshape the scientific community, as adoption grows and the word spreads.

For more socially-aware/activist researchers, the Mesh already has a strong value proposition. As privacy issues and the issues of security of data are of utmost importance in the European Union, the Science Mesh can offer a solution which works in conjunction with data sovereignty, rather than replacing it in the name of convenience. The Science Mesh follows a “privacy by design” philosophy, therefore protecting personal data by nature. It will also decrease the dependency on public cloud providers overseas, creating a pan-European space which can work within those legal boundaries. It is crucial that it offers a secure and private cloud system that responds to the needs of both EOSC and its users.

The Science Mesh also offers great opportunities in terms of economics and supporting the free market as well as fighting against monopolies and/or oligopolies, reshaping the research community and attracting more researchers from different fields. One of the ways it does it is by protecting researchers from “vendor lock-in”, which might otherwise lead to them becoming “hostage” to a given solution.

Monopoly and oligopoly are not efficient from an economics perspective as they can lead to manipulation of the market, especially against small, promising companies which try to compete with

larger, established ones. This is obviously against the principles of the free market. Initiatives like the Science Mesh contribute to a free market in cloud computing and storage, where small companies can exist and provide solutions or products for their users. This is ultimately beneficial to users as it will increase the product quality and decrease the costs.

5 Conclusions and Next Steps

This report's main goal is to compare the needs of the research community and their future expectations with what the Science Mesh offers, while considering how that differs from the services they are currently employing. In it, we answered two questions: (1) What are the opportunities the Science Mesh opens to users in the scientific community? (2) What are the challenges to adoption from the scientific community? We did this to understand the perspective of the scientific community concerning cloud computing; how researchers use cloud computing in their organizations for scientific purposes; which service they use; whether they are satisfied with their service providers in terms of storage limitations, costs, interoperability functions, speed of upload, and the future expectations and needs regarding them. Answering these questions will be critical for the Science Mesh, to identify the advantages, and challenges and adoption barriers that the project partners and early adopters face.

We find that the Science Mesh will grant researchers different capabilities that they can leverage to advance their research objectives. It would enable processes that individual researchers on their own would require much effort and cost to conduct. We find that the Mesh will enable researchers to transition easily from collecting and storing data to analysing data for new insights. Typically, researchers already store their data in the cloud. With the Mesh, these accumulated data in storage are given new life to realize applications previously unseen. Second, we find that the Mesh facilitates the connection of the individual with external actors. Like physical bridges that connect across islands, the Mesh will enable researchers to have a wider reach, beyond what they can typically "travel".

After running our interviews, we conceptualized the perceived challenges from the scientific community perspective, regarding the cloud services they are currently employing; these challenges, which align with the literature and are demonstrated to be real problems which users acknowledge, are namely data security, data privacy, vendor lock-in problems, reliability, performance issues, lack of flexibility and agility, data ownership problems, standardization issues, complexity, lack of flexibility and scalability, lack of service level agreements, and lack of interoperability. Therefore, this research report offered a very good opportunity to answer whether the Science Mesh could fulfil the needs of the scientific community and address those challenges.

While many previous studies have explored the barriers to data sharing (e.g., Beno et al. 2017; Van Panhuis et al. 2014), much work still needs to be done to accelerate the adoption of data sharing practices across research communities. Due to the connotations of the words "fair" and "open", many researchers tend to focus on the downsides of sharing data such as privacy, security, and scientific credit. Moreover, the narrative surrounding Open Science and FAIR data has overemphasized the collective benefits to the scientific community without focusing on the individual benefits for researchers (Staunton et al. 2021; Allen and Mehler 2019). Lost in this altruistic imperative, researchers can use these FAIR DIs to elevate their data analysis capabilities and augment their collaborations with research partners. Responding to this gap, our study explores whether and how DIs such as the Science Mesh can bring unique advantages to researchers.

Our study has implications for practice. Our study shifts the focus on FAIR data as an imperative for researchers to instead be an opportunity that they can take advantage of to further their research goals. The prevalent narrative of FAIR data and Open Science has centred around urging researchers to pursue them as they are the "*right thing to do*". In contrast, our research begins to frame these

movements as a unique source of competitive edge that researchers can leverage. To attract researchers to adopt FAIR, highlighting the advanced computational and collaborative functionalities it enables can be further explored.

Nevertheless, further studies are needed. The first limitation found herein was that the Science Mesh project is still being developed, meaning that a finalized product is not yet available for early adopters or the research community to test in their organizations. This makes the research process highly abstract, especially when the adoption barriers and advantages of the federated mesh are investigated. So far, the project management team and the early adopters who were interviewed tried to theoretically explain the advantages as they have not physically experienced or benefited from the product. Similarly, the barriers to the future adoption of the Science Mesh in the research community were investigated theoretically, through analysis of the literature and the expertise of the project partners. However, the challenges that occur during the Project implementation were experienced first-hand, therefore, these validated challenges can be addressed. Moreover, a larger sample size can also be pursued. In this report, 17 interviews were conducted with nine of them involving the research community with no previous information about the project. Since there is no established product, it is not possible at this moment to interview more early adopters to clarify the adoption barriers of the Science Mesh. On the other hand, the research community has limited knowledge of Open Science and interoperability, which made the interpretation of the interviews difficult to answer the question as to whether the Science Mesh is applicable in their research.

6 Guidelines towards adoption of the Science Mesh

The Science Mesh offers great opportunities to the scientific community; however, many adoption barriers were discussed in the “result” section. This section focuses on the recommendations to the Science Mesh Community to realize the project goals, to increase the interoperability between nodes, to contribute to Open Science and to make cloud storage services, in general, more effective in science.

Guideline 1: Create clear messaging on the value of the Mesh to researchers. In many of our interviews, it seems that many, even within the project, are not clear on how to sell the idea of the Mesh to the scientific community. A brief and straightforward description of its nature and benefits would benefit its adoption.

Guideline 2: Focus on current needs as a gateway to more advanced functionalities. Scientists engage with the cloud in specific ways, according to their domain needs. The long-tail of science uses the cloud mainly for storage while researchers in data-intensive applications would have more sophisticated application starting points. To compel these different users toward using the Mesh, the disruptions to their current workflows must be minimal. Only once they are in the Mesh ecosystem would it be more important to open the advanced functionalities offered through FAIR data and Open Science.

Guideline 3: Ride the wave of the Open Science and FAIR data movement. The Science Mesh is not alone in the promotion of Open Science and FAIR data; rather, it can use these parallel activities as a way to boost its adoption. With the effort by the EU to promote what open science is, why it is important, what FAIR Data is and how it will serve the goals of EOSC, the Science Mesh would be a natural complement to these discussions.

Guideline 4: Leverage organic adoption through network effects. The Mesh will connect seven services in research organizations in seven countries, namely SURFdrive (SURF, Netherlands), CERNBox (CERN), PSNCBox (PSNC, Poland), CloudStor (AARNET, Australia), Sciebo (WWU, Germany), CESNET (Czech Republic), SWITCHdrive (Switzerland), and ScienceData (DTU/DeiC, Denmark). As users

here would have to collaborate with other users who are not within these institutions, they can serve as an organic way to promote the adoption of the Mesh.

Guideline 5: Connect with multiple stakeholders to raise awareness. The marketing of the Science Mesh has been insufficient. The project team should focus on marketing the project through stakeholders who have relevant relationships with the scientific community. The project team can emphasize how interoperability works and indicate that their data is safe and secure even when researchers cooperate and have systems interoperate.

Stakeholder	Potential Go-to Strategy
Scientific community	Compel scientists using the Mesh to cite how it enabled their research workflows and collaborations in their papers. Identify and publicize data-intensive research groups in different domains to serve as examples.
Universities	Leverage introduction days in universities to introduce students to the Mesh. Hold workshops about the Mesh’s applications for students and administrators.
Research organizations	Use existing contacts in big science infrastructures as early demonstrators of the Mesh’s value. Identify influential groups within large organizations to use and try the Mesh.
IT Organizations	Website should have proper documentation so that IT departments can plug into the Mesh. Connect with the biggest academic organizations’ cloud service providers to ensure that they are pulled towards the Mesh.
Policy makers	Pair the Mesh with ongoing EOSC marketing initiatives Funding instruments can suggest mesh as a way to support Open Science.
Cloud Vendors	Create seal of approval to vendors supporting the Mesh.

Table 5. Stakeholder engagement.

To conclude, the Science Mesh is being built to link sync and share providers so that researchers can easily share data. Despite this, not all researchers are enthused by such a DI and the wider FAIR movement, in addition, they are wary of the costs required in its pursuit and the actual end benefits. To address this, we focus on the opportunities that FAIR data opens to researchers and how these capacities can be the source of unique research advantage.

7 References

- Allen, Christopher, and David M.A. Mehler. 2019. "Open Science Challenges, Benefits and Tips in Early Career and Beyond." *PLoS Biology*. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000246>.
- Almajalid, Rania. 2017. "A Survey on the Adoption of Cloud Computing in Education Sector," 1–12.
- Beno, Martin, Kathrin Figl, Jurgen Umbrich, and Axel Polleres. 2017. "Open Data Hopes and Fears: Determining the Barriers of Open Data." In *Proceedings of the 7th International Conference for E-Democracy and Open Government, CeDEM 2017*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CeDEM.2017.22>.
- Branco, Teófilo, Filipe De Sá-Soares, and Alfonso Lopez Rivero. 2017. "Key Issues for the Successful Adoption of Cloud Computing." *Procedia Computer Science* 121: 115–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2017.11.016>.
- Burgelman, Jean-Claude, Corina Pascu, Katarzyna Szkuta, Rene Von Schomberg, Athanasios Karalopoulos, Konstantinos Repanas, and Michel Schouppe. 2019. "Open Science, Open Data, and Open Scholarship: European Policies to Make Science Fit for the Twenty-First Century." *Frontiers in Big Data*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fdata.2019.00043>.
- Caldarelli, Adele, Luca Ferri, and Marco Maffei. 2017. "Expected Benefits and Perceived Risks of Cloud Computing: An Investigation within an Italian Setting." *Technology Analysis and Strategic Management* 29 (2): 167–80. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537325.2016.1210786>.
- Charlebois, Kathleen, Nicole Palmour, and Bartha Maria Knoppers. 2016. "The Adoption of Cloud Computing in the Field of Genomics Research: The Influence of Ethical and Legal Issues." *PLoS ONE* 11 (10): 1–33. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0164347>.
- Digital Science. 2018. "The State of Open Data."
- El-Gazzar, Rania, Eli Hustad, and Dag H. Olsen. 2016. "Understanding Cloud Computing Adoption Issues: A Delphi Study Approach." *Journal of Systems and Software* 118: 64–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2016.04.061>.
- EOSC. 2020. "Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Version 0.8 18 October 2020," no. October.
- European Commission. 2019. "Cost-Benefit Analysis for FAIR Research Data."
- . 2020. "Six Recommendations for Implementation of FAIR Practice." Luxembourg.
- Ferri, Luca, Rosanna Spanò, and Andrea Tomo. 2020. "Cloud Computing in High Tech Startups: Evidence from a Case Study." *Technology Analysis and Strategic Management* 32 (2): 146–57. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537325.2019.1641594>.
- Foster, Ian, Yong Zhao, Ioan Raicu, and Shiyong Lu. 2008. "Cloud Computing and Grid Computing 360-Degree Compared." In *2008 Grid Computing Environments Workshop*, 1–10. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/GCE.2008.4738445>.
- Geneviève, Lester Darryl, Andrea Martani, Maria Christina Mallet, Tenzin Wangmo, and Bernice Simone Elger. 2019. "Factors Influencing Harmonized Health Data Collection, Sharing and Linkage in Denmark and Switzerland: A Systematic Review." *PLoS ONE*.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0226015>.

- Gioia, Dennis A., Kevin G. Corley, and Aimee L. Hamilton. 2013. "Seeking Qualitative Rigor in Inductive Research: Notes on the Gioia Methodology." *Organizational Research Methods* 16 (1): 15–31. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428112452151>.
- Gupta, Prashant, A. Seetharaman, and John Rudolph Raj. 2013. "The Usage and Adoption of Cloud Computing by Small and Medium Businesses." *International Journal of Information Management* 33 (5): 861–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2013.07.001>.
- Houtkoop, Bobby Lee, Chris Chambers, Malcolm Macleod, Dorothy V.M. Bishop, Thomas E. Nichols, and Eric Jan Wagenmakers. 2018. "Data Sharing in Psychology: A Survey on Barriers and Preconditions." *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2515245917751886>.
- Jacobsen, Annika, Ricardo de Miranda Azevedo, Nick Juty, Dominique Batista, Simon Coles, Ronald Cornet, Mélanie Courtot, et al. 2020. "FAIR Principles: Interpretations and Implementation Considerations." *Data Intelligence*. https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_r_00024.
- Jankowski, Nicholas W. 2007. "Exploring E-Science: An Introduction." *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1083-6101.2007.00337.x>.
- Khanagha, Saeed, Shahzad Ansari, Sotirios Paroutis, and Luciano Oviedo. 2020. "Mutualism and the Dynamics of New Platform Creation: A Study of Cisco and Fog Computing." *Strategic Management Journal*, no. February: 1–31. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.3147>.
- Kurze, Tobias, Markus Klems, David Bermbach, Alexander Lenk, Stefan Tai, and Marcel Kunze. 2011. "Cloud Federation." *Computing*, no. c: 7.
- Lilleoere, Anne Mette, and Ebba Holme Hansen. 2011. "Knowledge-Sharing Enablers and Barriers in Pharmaceutical Research and Development." *Journal of Knowledge Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13673271111108693>.
- Madduri, Ravi, Kyle Chard, Mike D'arcy, Segun C. Jung, Alexis Rodriguez, Dinanath Sulakhe, Eric Deutsch, et al. 2019. "Reproducible Big Data Science: A Case Study in Continuous FAIRness." *PLoS ONE* 14 (4): 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0213013>.
- Mons, Barend, Cameron Neylon, Jan Velterop, Michel Dumontier, Luiz Olavo Bonino Da Silva Santos, and Mark D. Wilkinson. 2017. "Cloudy, Increasingly FAIR; Revisiting the FAIR Data Guiding Principles for the European Open Science Cloud." *Information Services and Use*. <https://doi.org/10.3233/ISU-170824>.
- Oliveira, Tiago, Manoj Thomas, and Mariana Espadanal. 2014. "Assessing the Determinants of Cloud Computing Adoption: An Analysis of the Manufacturing and Services Sectors." *Information and Management* 51 (5): 497–510. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2014.03.006>.
- Panhuis, Willem G. Van, Proma Paul, Claudia Emerson, John Grefenstette, Richard Wilder, Abraham J. Herbst, David Heymann, and Donald S. Burke. 2014. "A Systematic Review of Barriers to Data Sharing in Public Health." *BMC Public Health*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-14-1144>.
- Pankaj, Mehra, Katsaros Dimitrios, Vakali Athena, Pallis George, and D. Dikaiakos Marios. 2009. "Cloud Computing: Distributed Internet Computing for IT and Scientific Research." *IEEE Internet Computing* 37 (1): 10–13. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NNE.0b013e3182383371>.

- Philip Chen, C. L., and Chun Yang Zhang. 2014. "Data-Intensive Applications, Challenges, Techniques and Technologies: A Survey on Big Data." *Information Sciences* 275: 314–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2014.01.015>.
- Romasanta, Angelo, and Jonathan Wareham. 2021. "FAIR DATA THROUGH A FEDERATED CLOUD INFRASTRUCTURE: EXPLORING THE SCIENCE MESH." In *ECIS 2021 Research-in-Progress Papers*, 14.
- Ross, Peter K., and Michael Blumenstein. 2015. "Cloud Computing as a Facilitator of SME Entrepreneurship." *Technology Analysis and Strategic Management* 27 (1): 87–101. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537325.2014.951621>.
- Rowhani-Farid, Anisa, Michelle Allen, and Adrian G. Barnett. 2017. "What Incentives Increase Data Sharing in Health and Medical Research? A Systematic Review." *Research Integrity and Peer Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-017-0028-9>.
- Sadashiv, Naidila, and S. M. Dilip Kumar. 2011. "Cluster, Grid and Cloud Computing: A Detailed Comparison." *ICCSE 2011 - 6th International Conference on Computer Science and Education, Final Program and Proceedings*, no. Iccse: 477–82. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCSE.2011.6028683>.
- "Science Mesh : Enabling Seamless Research Collaborations through a Federated Cloud Infrastructure." n.d., no. Ecis 2021: 1–9.
- Sharma, Sujeet Kumar, Ali H. Al-Badi, Srikrishna Madhumohan Govindaluri, and Mohammed H. Al-Kharusi. 2016. "Predicting Motivators of Cloud Computing Adoption: A Developing Country Perspective." *Computers in Human Behavior* 62: 61–69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2016.03.073>.
- Staunton, Ciara, Carlos Andrés Barragán, Stefano Canali, Calvin Ho, Sabina Leonelli, Matthew Mayernik, Barbara Prainsack, and Ambroise Wonkham. 2021. "Open Science, Data Sharing and Solidarity: Who Benefits?" *History and Philosophy of the Life Sciences* 43 (4): 115. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40656-021-00468-6>.
- Sultan, Nabil. 2010. "Cloud Computing for Education: A New Dawn?" *International Journal of Information Management* 30 (2): 109–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2009.09.004>.
- Tenopir, Carol, Elizabeth D. Dalton, Suzie Allard, Mike Frame, Ivanka Pjesivac, Ben Birch, Danielle Pollock, and Kristina Dorsett. 2015. "Changes in Data Sharing and Data Reuse Practices and Perceptions among Scientists Worldwide." *PLoS ONE*. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0134826>.
- Toosi, Adel Nadjaran, Rodrigo N. Calheiros, and Rajkumar Buyya. 2014. "Interconnected Cloud Computing Environments." *ACM Computing Surveys* 47 (1): 1–47. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2593512>.
- Vicente-Saez, Ruben, and Clara Martinez-Fuentes. 2018. "Open Science Now: A Systematic Literature Review for an Integrated Definition." *Journal of Business Research* 88 (July): 428–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2017.12.043>.
- Walport, Mark, and Paul Brest. 2011. "Sharing Research Data to Improve Public Health." *The Lancet*. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(10\)62234-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(10)62234-9).

- Wilkinson, Mark D., Michel Dumontier, IJsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, Gabrielle Appleton, Myles Axton, Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg, et al. 2016. "The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship." *Scientific Data* 3 (1): 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.
- Wise, John, Alexandra Grebe de Barron, Andrea Splendiani, Beeta Balali-Mood, Drashtti Vasant, Eric Little, Gaspare Mellino, et al. 2019. "Implementation and Relevance of FAIR Data Principles in Biopharmaceutical R&D." *Drug Discovery Today* 24 (4): 933–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drudis.2019.01.008>.
- Yang, Xiaoyu, Bassem Nasser, Mike Surrige, and Stuart Middleton. 2012. "A Business-Oriented Cloud Federation Model for Real-Time Applications." *Future Generation Computer Systems* 28 (8): 1158–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2012.02.005>.
- Yang, Xiaoyu, David Wallom, Simon Waddington, Jianwu Wang, Arif Shaon, Brian Matthews, Michael Wilson, et al. 2014. "Cloud Computing in E-Science: Research Challenges and Opportunities." *Journal of Supercomputing* 70 (1): 408–64. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11227-014-1251-5>.
- Zhang, Zhizhong, Chuan Wu, and David W.L. Cheung. 2013. "A Survey on Cloud Interoperability: Taxonomies, Standards, and Practice." *Performance Evaluation Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2479942.2479945>.

Annex

Interview questions

Part I: Cloud storage overview

- What is the current cloud storage setup in your institution?
- When it comes to cloud services, how much of the decision is made by the research group? How about the research organization? Could you talk about the interaction between researchers and the IT organization with respect to the cloud?
- How is cloud storage typically used?
- What are the typical challenges?

Part II: Science Mesh

- What is the use case of the Mesh in your organization?
- How is this workflow currently being done without the Mesh? What will the workflow be with the Mesh?
- What are the main advantages of this new workflow versus the older one?

Part III: Issues and challenges

- What are the adoption challenges that you foresee for a solution like the Mesh?
- What do you think about the following issues? How concerned are you about them?
 - General concerns
 - Privacy/security
 - Legal
 - Cost-related
 - Technology characteristics
 - Relative advantage (e.g., Convenience, enabling new research opportunities)
 - Complexity
 - Compatibility
 - Technology maturity
 - Organizational context
 - Freedom to choose technologies
 - Vendor lock-in / switching costs
 - Incentives towards data sharing
 - Environmental context
 - Interoperability
 - Collaboration barriers
 - Data FAIRness
- What are the features you would like to have in future cloud storage services?
- What are the technological developments you are excited about with respect to the cloud?